

Dairy Value Chain Analysis: A Case Study of Diredawa City

**Agriculture Water Mines and Energy Development Bureau of
Diredawa Administration**

**By: Adamu Girma
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Adamu Girma¹

¹Animal and Plant Health and Regulatory Department; Agriculture, Water, Mines and Energy Bureau of Diredawa Administration; P.O.Box 449, Diredawa, Ethiopia. Tel: (251)-25-111 1306; Email:

adam_girm@yahoo.com

Abstract

The study was conducted to characterize the dairy value chain, to identify the actors involved and their roles, and to assess the challenges and opportunities for development of the dairy industry in Dire Dawa city, Eastern Ethiopia. A total of nineteen key informants (fifteen urban milk producers and four milk vendors) were interviewed using a structured questionnaire. In addition to the primary data generated through survey, secondary data were collected from various reports published about the study area and through consultation of concerned individuals and institutions. The results of the study indicated that the dairy value chain is not well organized in Dire Dawa. The roles and functions of all the actors in the value chain are not clear and there is a weak link between milk producers, traders and all stakeholders of the Dire Dawa dairy sector. The Dire Dawa dairy industry is constrained by various socio-economic, institutional, organizational and technical problems. Shortage and high cost of feed, lack of organization that provides dairy related information, difficulty to get land, disease prevalence, lack of technical support, and lack of dairy related technologies are the major constraints related to milk production whereas problems related to milk marketing include lack of quality control of milk, lack of cooling and storage facilities at milk vending sites, poor quality of milk supplied from rural areas, sale of raw milk, inappropriate milk handling and storage vessels, and spoilage of milk due to lack of preservation and processing facilities. The major opportunities for the development of the dairy sector in Dire Dawa include high demand for milk, presence of enabling policy that encourages investment in the dairy sector, absence of competitors, and access to road, train and air transportation systems that gives easy market access to dairy products. Thus, in order to develop the dairy industry of Dire Dawa, all the challenges identified in this study need to be carefully considered and addressed. Moreover, possible intervention strategies should be designed and applied across the entire value chain in order to develop the Dire Dawa dairy industry.

1. Introduction

Ethiopia has the largest livestock population in Africa, estimated at 45,054 969 cattle, 20,562,832 sheep, 20,191,099 goats and 1,490,982 camels (MoARD, 2007). Recent figures indicate that the livestock sector contributes about 12-16% of national GDP, 30-35% of agricultural GDP (MoARD, 2007), 15% of export earnings and 30% of agricultural employment (SNV, 2008). Livestock contribute to the livelihoods of 60-70% of the population (Aklilu, 2002).

The livestock sector in general and the dairy industry in particular do not make the expected contribution to the national income despite their large numbers due to several factors. The development of the dairy sector in the country is hindered by a number of technical, institutional and socio-economic constraints. The growth in milk production has been slow and the annual milk production is estimated to be 1,089,488,251 liters (MoARD, 2007) which doesn't meet even the domestic demand for dairy products. As a result the country imports large volumes of dairy products per annum to meet the domestic demand. In 2005, for instance, the country imported 457,260 kg of milk (liquid and powder) which is equivalent to 3,026,724 Birr (MoARD, 2007). The dairy sector is dominated by smallholder farmers who account for about 85% of the population and are responsible for 98% of the milk production (MoARD, 2007).

Rapidly increasing population size with a growing urbanization is resulting in a growing demand for dairy products in Ethiopia. Dairy development can lead to growth in rural areas by increasing farm income and employment opportunities. Besides low milk production levels, milk collection, processing and marketing are not well developed in the country. A chain approach aimed at sustainable development of the dairy sector is lacking.

To build a successful and sustainable dairy industry, all parts of possible entry points for intervention across the milk value chain have to be identified; from cow to consumer. Different parts of the value chain need different kinds of support and intervention where the situation of course requires various case to case interventions. Several entry points could be identified across the dairy value chain with varied degree of resource requirement and levels of competition.

Dire Dawa is the second largest city in Ethiopia and has a human population 342,827 that grows at a rate of 2.5% per annum (CSA, 2008). Thus given its population size, there is high demand for milk and milk products in Dire Dawa. However, the annual milk production in Dire Dawa was reported to be 2,643,000 liters (CSA, 2010), which is far below its demand. To date, there is no information regarding the dairy value chain in Dire Dawa. Thus, investigation of the dairy value chain in Dire Dawa will help to identify

possible entry points for intervention across the milk value chain and thereby contribute to the development of the dairy industry. This study was, therefore, designed with the following objectives.

1.1. Objectives

- To determine the dairy value chain in Dire Dawa, identify the actors involved, and understand their functions and linkages between them.
- To identify the challenges and opportunities for development of the dairy industry in Dire Dawa.
- To recommend intervention strategies aimed at improving the effectiveness of the dairy value chain and development of the dairy sector in Dire Dawa area.

2. Description of the Study Area

The study was conducted in Dire Dawa city. Dire Dawa is located in eastern part of Ethiopia between 9027'E and 49'N latitude and between 41038' N and 19'E longitude at a distance of 515 km from the capital Addis Ababa (DDACAO, 1998). The administrative region is estimated to have a total land area of 128, 802 ha of which 97.73% covers the rural area and the remaining 2.27% accounts for the land area used by the region's main urban center, Dire Dawa city (DDPAIA, 2005).

The climatic condition of Dire Dawa Administrative Region seems to be greatly influenced by its topography, which lies between 950–1250 masl, and which is characterized by warm and dry climate with a relatively low level of precipitation. The mean annual temperature of Dire Dawa is about 25.4°C. The average maximum temperature of the administrative region is 31.4°C, while its average minimum temperature is about 18.2°C. The region has two rainy seasons; that is, a small rain occurs from March to April, and a main shower of rain that extends from August to September. The aggregate average annual rainfall that the region gets from these two seasons is about 604 mm. On the other hand, the region is believed to have an abundant underground water resource (DDPAIA, 2005).

About 73.6% of the population of the region resides in urban areas and the rest 26.4% live in rural areas. Being one of the largest urban centers in the country, Dire Dawa has become home for people from different nations and nationalities found in the country as well as for people from India, Yemen, Turkey, etc. (DDPAIA, 2005). Islam and Christianity are the predominant religions practiced in the region.

3. Methodology

3.1. Sampling Method, Data Collection and Analysis

Purposive sampling method based on production of milk and possession of crossbred/grade dairy cows, and involvement in the sale of milk, respectively was employed to select dairy farms and milk vendors found in Dire Dawa city. The dairy farms and milk vendors found in Dire Dawa were identified with the help of the Dire Dawa Investment and Agriculture Bureaus. A cross-sectional survey (key-informant survey) was carried out among the major dairy farms (fifteen) and milk vendors (four) from April 2010 to June 2010 using a single-visit multiple-response survey method (ILCA, 1990) in order to understand and describe the dairy value chain and the various actors involved in the value chain. Separate semi-structured questionnaires were developed and administered to farm owners and milk vendors (traders) found in Dire Dawa city. In addition to the primary data generated through survey, secondary data was collected from reports published about the study area and through consultation of concerned individuals in public institutions. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data using SPSS software version 12.0.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. The Dairy Value Chain in Dire Dawa

Figure 1 illustrates the typical dairy value chain of Dire Dawa city. The major actors of the dairy value chain in Dire Dawa include input suppliers, service providers, milk producers (urban and subsistent rural dairy farmers), wholesalers, retailers and consumers. The input suppliers are those agents who supply inputs such as animal feed, forage seeds, veterinary drugs and AI services to dairy farmers whereas service providers are institutions who provide technical support (professional advice and training), technological packages and credit (loan) to the producers. Wholesalers are milk vendors who collect (buy) milk from individual rural producers and deliver the milk to customers (retailers) in Dire Dawa town. The retailers buy milk either from urban dairy farms or wholesalers who supply rural milk and sale the milk to individual consumers at higher price. The retailers involved in milk marketing in Dire Dawa include small milk shops (kiosks), restaurants, cafeterias and hotels.

Figure 1. The Dairy Value Chain in Dire Dawa

There is generally weak link between urban milk producers and service providers (universities/colleges, bureau of agriculture and investment office). The urban milk producers complain that they do not get services such as technical support, technological packages and credit from the concerned institutions. Milk suppliers need to have technical support on the process of production including feeding and nutrition, breeding, sanitation and milk hygiene, human and animal health, marketing and handling and transportation of milk towards collection centers (SNV, 2008). Through appropriate technical support and capacity improvement, the problem of the milk value chain, i.e., shortage of raw milk supply and access to reach the market could be tackled. Thus, there is an urgent need to create effective and functional linkages between milk producers, service providers and all institutions involved in the development of the dairy sector in Dire Dawa. Possible interventions in the supply side could be strengthening of raw milk supply, establishment of milk collection centers, and provision of feed, logistics and dairy breeds.

4.2. Milk Production and Supply in Dire Dawa

There are two types of milk producers (suppliers) in Dire Dawa: private urban milk producers and rural smallholder subsistent farmers. The average daily milk yield, number of milking cows, lactation length and calving interval of both local and crossbred cows are indicated in Table 1. At the time of this study, there were 15 major dairy farms in

Dire Dawa city that possess crossbred/grade dairy cows. These farms use crossbred (Holstein-Friesian vs Zebu or Jersey vs Zebu cattle) for milk production under stall feeding management system. Apart from these major dairy farms, indigenous cows owned by individual households also produce milk in the city.

Table1. Productive and reproductive performance of local and crossbred cows in Dire Dawa city

Variables	Breed of cows	
	Local	Crossbred/Grade
Number of cows	37129	730
Daily milk yield (L/cow)	2	16.5
Lactation length (days)	150	195
Lactation milk yield (L/cow)	300	3217
Calving interval (days)	912	547

L = Liter.

The amount of milk produced per day/cow by local cows in the present study (Table 1) is lower than the value 2.8 kg milk/head/day reported for local Zebu breed by Kiwuwa *et al.* (1983). However, the daily milk yield of crossbred cows observed in the present study is much higher than the value 5.6 kg/head/day reported by Kiwuwa *et al.* (1983) for crossbred cows (Zebu x exotic F1 crosses) in Arsi highlands of Ethiopia. The high daily milk yield observed in crossbred cows in the present study might be attributed to the high grade animals used by producers in Dire Dawa city. About 73.6% of the Dire Dawa population reside in urban areas and the rest 26.4% live in rural areas. So, in view of Dire Dawa's population, the amount of milk produced currently in the city is much below its demand. This suggests a need for increasing milk production in order to meet the increasing demand for milk in the city.

The lactation length of local cows was only five months and that of crossbred cows was 6.5 months (Table 1). These figures are below the national averages for lactation length of local cows (239 days) (Mukasa-Mugerewa and Tegegne, 1989) and crossbred cows (279 days) (Ahmed *et al.*, 2004). The lactation milk yield of local (300 liters) and crossbred (3217 liter) cows observed in this study are also below the values 400-680 liters and 1120-2500 liters of milk/cow reported by Ahmed *et al.* (2004), respectively. The calving interval (CI) for local cows was found to be 34 months and that of crossbred cows was 18.2 months (Table 1), values which are much longer than CI (25 months) reported for highland Zebu cattle (Mukassu-Mugerewa, 1989) and CI (15.3 months) reported for Friesian x Zebu crosses (Kiwuwa *et al.*, 1983). The short lactation length and the long calving interval observed may have been attributed to the relatively poor management conditions and poor plane of nutrition of the cows in the study area (Section

3.4). Plane of nutrition is a major factor that determines the productive and reproductive performances of dairy cows (Ahmed *et al.*, 2004).

Urban dairy farms are the major milk producers in Dire Dawa. However, significant amount of milk is also supplied to Dire Dawa city from smallholder subsistent farmers located at a radius of 85 km. The major rural producers who supply milk to Dire Dawa city are indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Peri-urban milk suppliers to Dire Dawa city

Variables	Response
Cow milk suppliers	Kulubi Lange Kersa Garamuleta Melka Jebdu Hurso
Cow and camel milk suppliers	Babile Erer Shinile
Milk containers used	Plastic bottles (Jerican) Un-refrigerated open vehicles
Mode of transportation	(Minibuses)

Even though the rural milk producers supply large amount of milk to Dire Dawa consumers, the quality of milk supplied from this source is generally poor. Milk is transported by placing it in plastic containers (bottles) from a place as far as 85 km away from Dire Dawa city using un-refrigerated open vehicles (minibuses) at ambient temperature. Thus, by the time the milk arrives at Dire Dawa market, large proportion of the milk gets spoiled and as a result Dire Dawa consumers often avoid such milk the result of which is considerable financial loss to the producer (trader).

4.3. Milk Marketing in Dire Dawa

The dairy farmers in Dire Dawa have only two market-outlets for selling their milk. These are selling to neighbors (i.e., individual consumers) and retailers. There is no formal milk marketing system both in the urban and peri-urban areas of Dire Dawa. That is, there is no well-organized milk marketing system in Dire Dawa. Traditional/informal milk markets have played a key role in dairy development in Ethiopia. Informal, small-scale markets control over 90% of marketed milk in the country. Producers sale their milk to anyone whom they come across every day. Debrah and Berhanu (1991) reported

that producers' knowledge of alternative sales outlets and of price they get will generally enhance their bargaining position and improve their chances of getting the highest prices for their products. Producers will also have the flexibility to shift between outlets to obtain best prices (Belachew, 1997). At the time of this study, there were only two dairy cooperatives (Adis Alem and Goro Dairy Cooperatives) which were established in 2007 and 2010, respectively by the NGO Jerusalem Children and Community Development Organization (JeCCDO) that is engaged mainly in capacity building of the community. The milk producers in Dire Dawa do not get the benefit that they would get otherwise and do not have a guaranty for selling their products especially at times of low demand for milk in the market. Debrah and Berhanu (1991) reported that large producers opted to market most of their output through outlets that guaranteed stability of purchase even if it was less remunerative than if sales were made directly to individual consumers.

Dairy cooperatives and formation of milk groups help reduce transportation cost and save time. It also gives producers a guaranteed access to market and sell their milk. Establishment of milk groups and cooperatives as well as milk-collection centers can give dairy farmers a broader choice of marketing their milk instead of depending on local traders and neighborhood buyers. Thus, one entry point for intervention to improve the dairy sector in Dire Dawa is establishment of and strengthening the existing dairy cooperatives. Therefore, this calls for an integrated action towards this end by all concerned bodies. The JeCCDO initiative in this regard is a good start that needs to be supported by others too. The successful dairy cooperatives and milk groups formed by farmers in Selale and Ada'a areas of the country (Tsehay, 1998) could serve as a good example of success stories for dairy farmers in Dire Dawa. Dairy co-operatives and milk groups have facilitated the participation of smallholders in fluid milk markets in the Ethiopian highlands (SNV, 2008). Evidence from Kenya emphasizes the importance of milk collection organizations in improving access to market and expanding productive bases (SNV, 2008).

Currently, there is no milk processing plant in Dire Dawa. As a result, consumers do not have any chance to buy different processed dairy products based on their preference. The Dire Dawa market is dominated by fluid milk, thus processed dairy products such as cheese and butter, etc. are rarely found on the market. This is a good opportunity for potential investors interested to establish milk processing plants in Dire Dawa, in fact, provided that other factors in particular milk yield is sufficient and there is reliable supply of milk.

The major sales outlets of milk produced in Dire Dawa are retailers (small milk shops), cafeterias, restaurants, hotels and individual consumers who buy milk at farm gate (Table

3). Urban milk producers sale one liter of milk for 8 Ethiopian Birr¹ whereas the price of one liter of milk sold by retailers (traders) was on the average 9.5 Birr. On the other hand, the quantity of milk sold per day per farm was on the average 137 liters while milk vendors sale about eight liters of milk per day. Debrah and Berhanu (1991) reported that significant variations were observed in price charged or paid for fresh milk sold through alternative marketing systems, type of producer and outlet used.

Table 3. Price, transportation cost, mode of transport and sales outlets of milk within Dire Dawa city

Market Agent	Sales outlet	Price/L (Birr)	Average Qt Sold/d/f or /t (L)	Mode of Payment	Mode & Average Transport Cost (Birr/month)
Producers (n =15)		8	120.5		
	Individual consumers			Cash	Badjaj (1291.7)
	Retailers (milk shops)			Cash in advance	Horse cart (1500)
	Cafeteria				Bicycle (360)
	Restaurants Hotels				Own vehicle
Traders (n = 4)		9.5	8.3		
	Individual consumers			Cash	

n = number of respondents; L = liter; d = day; f = farm; t = trader.

Most customers in Dire Dawa buy milk from urban dairy farms by paying cash on daily basis. However, some customers pay the monthly amount in advance which they call it contract payment where in fact there was no any formal contractual agreement between the producers and buyers in the strict sense of the term. Urban milk producers deliver milk to their clients on daily basis using Badjaj (three wheeled scooter), horse cart, bicycle or using their own vehicle. The average monthly transportation cost paid for Badjaj was higher than the other means of transportation (Table 3).

In order to develop the dairy industry in Dire Dawa, dairy supply and marketing systems need to undertake radical changes. For such changes to occur, development of market-oriented dairy farming system is a prerequisite. In order to convince farmers to follow such approach, creation of awareness and education of farmers need immediate attention.

4.4. Constraints to the Dairy Sector

In Ethiopia, the livestock sector in general and the dairy sub-sector in particular do not make a substantial contribution to the national income, despite its large size, due to

¹ The exchange rate of US Dollar to Ethiopian Birr at the time of this study was 1 US Dollar = 13.56 Ethiopian Birr.

numerous socio-environmental factors. The poor performance of the dairy sub-sector can also be attributed to socio-economic, infrastructure and technical constraints, inadequate research and extension activities, and lack of policies relevant to the development of the dairy industry (SNV, 2008). Among others, land tenure policies, feed availability, lack of adequate dairy services, lack of marketing outlets, and poor roads and transportation systems are the major constraints of the dairy sector in three East African countries viz., Ethiopia, Kenya and Uganda (SNV, 2008).

One of the major constraints that the urban milk producers of Dire Dawa are encountered with is lack of access to land for establishment of a dairy farm and for forage production. Large proportion (57%) of the respondents indicated that it is very difficult to get land for establishment of dairy farm in Dire Dawa (Figure 2). This problem seems to occur mainly due to bureaucracy to get land for investment, failure to appreciate the positive contribution of a viable dairy industry to the national economy by regional decision makers, and also due to the low attention given to the dairy industry. Reports indicate that the greatest institutional and socio-economic constraint that the dairy industry faces today arises out of socio-economic rather than technical problems; i.e., lack of access to land for expansion of the dairy enterprises and feed production (SNV, 2008). The problem of inadequate feed in the country is a result of the limited land availability for pasture establishment especially on productive highland areas where dairy cattle can flourish and where the density of the population is high. Thus, all concerned bodies should work hard to solve this policy (land tenure) related problem and encourage potential investors interested to engage in the dairy sector.

Another important problem reported by almost all the respondents (100%) was feed shortage, i.e., low supply and high cost especially of agro-industrial by-products (Figure 2). Most dairy farmers of Dire Dawa purchase feed for their dairy animals from Addis Ababa which is located at a distance of 515 km and transport it all the way to Dire Dawa the transportation cost of which is almost comparable to the cost of the feed itself. Inadequate supply of quality feed is the major factor limiting dairy productivity in Ethiopia (SNV, 2008). Improved feeding is crucial to for satisfactory animal growth and feed supplements stimulate higher milk production. Feed, usually based on fodder and grass, are either not available in sufficient quantities due to fluctuating weather conditions or when available are of poor nutritional quality. These constraints result in low milk yield, high mortality of young stock, longer parturition intervals, and low animal weight.

In the highlands of Ethiopia, high population growth and density are causing shortage of grazing land on which livestock production by smallholders depends. In the lowland areas, the shortages of feed and water during the dry season forces animals and livestock

keepers to trek long distances in search of feed and water. The quality of feed also deteriorates during the dry season in both the mixed farming and pastoral systems. Apart from this, there is critical shortage and high cost of feed. Besides, there are only few companies that produce feed concentrates and therefore dairy processing plants depend on farmers' scanty produce.

Among the different types of animal feeds used, supply of grass hay is very limited in Dire Dawa. Thus, production of forage/pasture species specially adapted to Dire Dawa climate could be one possible solution to overcome the limited supply of hay in the area. Establishment of animal feed processing plants in the vicinity of Dire Dawa may solve the problem of high transportation cost of agro-industrial by-products.

Feed supply is a major issue for smallholder dairy systems, as most systems operate under conditions of extreme land pressure. Feed conservation for dry season supplementation has been a major issue, as most technologies such as silage, haymaking, and urea treatment are not suitable for smallholders (SNV, 2008). Fodder trees and mixed tree-legume protein banks can be a solution. Hence, improved nutrition through adoption of sown forage and better crop residue management and use can substantially raise livestock productivity.

Currently, there is no any agent or institution that monitors and controls the quality and safety of milk sold to Dire Dawa consumers. Some respondents indicated that there is a possibility that milk obtained from cows infected with zoonotic diseases such as tuberculosis can be sold on the market. Thus, the absence of milk quality control on the market is a very serious problem that could pose high public health risk which may one day result in a catastrophic outbreak of dangerous milk-borne diseases in the area. Therefore, this potential health hazard (risk) can be prevented by putting in place appropriate regulatory mechanisms in order to monitor and control the safety of milk sold to the consumers in Dire Dawa. Hence, there is an urgent need to establish milk quality control and regulation mechanisms in the area.

Many of the milk producers (57%) indicated that they often do not get the support they need from the concerned institutions (organizations) (Figure 2). They indicated that they are badly in need of services such as professional advices (training on basic milk/dairy production techniques), readily available technological packages and loan (credit) from service providers in order to run their business successfully; however, there is weak link between milk producers and the service providers in Dire Dawa. Thus, coordination and creation of sustainable linkage between producers and service providers is one priority area of intervention in order to develop the dairy sector in Dire Dawa.

Even though all the dairy farmers of Dire Dawa reported that veterinarians often check the health of their animals and periodically give them vaccinations against the most common diseases of dairy cows, some of the dairy farmers reported incidence of diseases such as mastitis and other zoonotic diseases of public health concern in their dairy herds. Poor animal health and management are major constraints of dairy development in Ethiopia which cause poor performance across all dairy production systems (SNV, 2008). Many of the disease constraints which affect milk supply are also attributed to insufficient money to purchase drugs or vaccines by the owners. Some of the dairy farmers (28.6%) of Dire Dawa mentioned high medical and/or multi-vitamin cost as important constraint that affects their farm business. Thus, this calls for the need for good and easily accessible veterinary services in the area.

Dairy farmers who use artificial insemination to breed their animals reported a major fertility problem in their dairy herds. They indicated a very high service to conception rate in their herd the cause of which has not yet been identified. Some farmers also reported the problem of detecting cows on heat. The high service to conception rate observed could partly be attributed to failures to detect cows on heat and it might also be due to poor quality of the semen used. In general, the underlying cause of low fertility of cows associated with the use of artificial insemination needs careful investigation. There is also a need to give farmers training on mating and heat detection techniques.

Some respondents indicated seasonal decline in demand for milk in Dire Dawa. They mentioned that the demand for milk decreases during fasting periods especially among those consumers who are followers of the Orthodox Christian faith who do not consume animal products including milk and milk products during fasting seasons and fasting days. In Ethiopia, orthodox Christians (about 35-40 percent of the population) are abstained from consuming dairy products for more than 200 days every year (Tsehay, 2001).

Capital requirements for establishing dairy farms/plants are generally high and may be especially constraining for smallholder farmers. Some of the respondents (10%) in the present study indicated that one of the constraints for engaging in dairy business is that it requires high initial capital (Figure 2). Formation of institutional credit schemes may help some smallholders to engage in a dairy business.

A closer observation of the dairy industry of Dire Dawa revealed that there is no institution responsible for keeping dairy related records (databases) that would provide reliable, up-to-date and consistent information regarding the dairy sector. As a result, it is very difficult to get dairy farm or product related information in Dire Dawa. Thus, establishment of a dairy board at national or regional (Dire Dawa) levels as is the case in other African countries such as Kenya may solve this problem.

Figure 2. Major constraints associated with production and sale of dairy products in Dire Dawa

Constraints related to sale of milk and milk products encountered by milk traders of Dire Dawa are indicated in Figure 2. Some of the problems encountered by the traders are similar to problems that milk producers face whereas some problems are unique to the milk vendors. Lack of quality control of milk, milk spoilage, sale of raw/unpasteurized milk and seasonal decline in demand for milk are problems that traders share with milk producers. Whereas lack of milk cooling, storage, preservation and processing facilities and consequent deterioration of milk quality, and inappropriate storage vessels and handling of milk are problems peculiar to the milk vendors. Thus, building the capacity of milk vendors (traders) by providing facilities for milk cooling and storage and establishing milk collection or vending centers may help alleviate some of the problems that the milk vendors face in Dire Dawa.

4.5. SWOT Analysis of the Dire Dawa Dairy Sector

Table 4 presents the results of the SWOT analysis of the dairy sector of Dire Dawa. The weaknesses and threats of the dairy sector indicated in Table 4 are basically similar to the constraints of the dairy sector discussed in Section 3.4 above. The strengths of the dairy industry of Dire Dawa are the attractive price of milk and availability of cheap labor for dairy farms and milk vending activities.

The high demand for milk, milk consumption tradition of the society and presence of people with different cultural and religious backgrounds in Dire Dawa give opportunities that will attract potential investors to establish dairy farms and milk processing plants in Dire Dawa. This in turn will positively contribute to the development of the Dire Dawa dairy industry.

Currently, there is no any milk processing plant in Dire Dawa. Thus, this could also be considered as an opportunity for potential investors because they will have fewer competitors in the sector that would affect marketing of their products.

The Government of Ethiopia is encouraging investments in the agricultural sector. Hence, presence of enabling policy environment is also an opportunity for the growth of the dairy industry in Dire Dawa. The location of Dire Dawa is another opportunity for the development of the dairy industry. Dire Dawa has access to road (bus), train and air transportation systems and thus this will give a good opportunity for marketing dairy products both in the domestic and export markets.

Table 4. *SWOT analysis of the dairy sector in Dire Dawa*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Response</i>
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attractive milk price Cheap farm labour
Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Absence of quality control for milk Low milk production Shortage of skilled/trained staff Difficulty to get land Limited supply and high feed cost Absence of milk processing plants Poor quality raw milk Lack of cooling & storage facilities Incidence of animal diseases Absence of dairy cooperatives/milk groups Lack of milk collection centers Lack of reliable, up-to-date & consistent information
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High demand for milk Milk consumption tradition of the society Presence of people with d/t cultures & religion Less competitors in the dairy sector Conducive investment policy Access to air, train and bus transportation systems
Threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sale of raw/unpasteurized milk Low demand for milk during fasting periods & rainy seasons The high ambient temperature of the area

5. Conclusions

The dairy value chain in Dire Dawa is not well organized. The roles and functions of all actors in the value chain are not clear and there is weak link between milk producers, traders and all stakeholders of the dairy industry in the area. Thus, there is a need to develop an effective and functioning linkage between all the stakeholders in the value chain in Dire Dawa. In order to develop the dairy sector in Dire Dawa, there is a need to consider the weaknesses and threats of the dairy sector identified in this study. Besides, possible intervention strategies should be applied along the entire value chain in order to bring about positive change in the dairy industry in the area.

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations are forwarded in order to develop the Dire Dawa dairy sector:

- Analysis of the dairy value chain of Dire Dawa shows a weak link between milk producers and service and input suppliers. Investment in dairy development through provision of appropriate credit and research technologies to smallholder producers will bring growth and shift producers towards greater commercial orientation, increasing their demand for improved technologies and innovations. Thus, coordination and creation of effective and functional linkages between producers and all actors across the dairy value chain in Dire Dawa is essential.
- The Dire Dawa dairy sector is dominated by traditional informal marketing system. Traditional informal markets have clearly provided an effective, functional link between farmers and consumers which responds to consumer demand: Moreover, such markets are generally those most often serving the needs of small-scale farmers and resource-poor consumers. Therefore, public policy-makers should work hard to develop formal milk marketing systems in Dire Dawa and engage constructively with traditional markets to link them with formal modern industry.
- Dairy co-operatives have played a significant role in fostering dairy development, primarily by providing a stable market environment and delivering services to farmers. They played key role in linking poor farmers to input and output markets. Currently there are only two dairy cooperatives established recently and no milk collection center in Dire Dawa. Therefore, establishment of and strengthening of the existing milk cooperatives and milk collection centers should be the first priority of those concerned with the development of the dairy sector in the area.
- At present, there is no milk processing plant in Dire Dawa and the Dire Dawa market is dominated only by fluid milk. Hence, this is a good opportunity for potential investors interested to invest on milk processing in Dire Dawa.
- All concerned offices should provide support services to increase clean milk production. An effective and well-trained animal health professionals should be available at any time to look after the health of dairy animals and arrangements should be made for regular vaccination and checking against contagious diseases by the qualified veterinarians.
- Formation of Dire Dawa Dairy Board is important in order to provide reliable, up-to-date and consistent information related to the dairy sector.

- Addressing milk quality concerns and transforming the informal milk markets based on the concept of business development services that are supervised by national regulatory authorities are important. The absence of an institution (organization) responsible for controlling and regulating the quality of milk produced and sold on the market in Dire Dawa calls for the need to establish milk quality control mechanisms in the region.

- The results of this study indicated that the hygienic quality of milk produced in Dire Dawa is poor. Thus, training milk producers and traders on basic dairy farming practices and milk hygiene is essential to insure clean milk production in the area.

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Appendix

Key Informant Interviews to Collect Information about Dairy Marketing/Value Chain in Dire Dawa City

A. GENERAL INFORMATION

Date: _____

1. Name of key informant/marketing agent: _____

2. Location/address: _____

3. Type of marketing agent: a). Producer, b). Wholesaler, c). Retailer,
d). Itinerant trader, e). Catering shop, f). Private processing plant,
g). Government processing plant, h). Cooperative processing plant,
i). Other (specify): _____

4. Sex: a). Male b). Female

5. Age of decision maker _____yrs.

6. Education: a). No formal b) Adult literacy c). Primary d). Secondary
e). Beyond secondary

B. PRODUCER/FARMER

7. Type of producer: a). Specialized dairy farmer
b). Crop-livestock farmer
c). Small/landless dairy farmer
d). Agro-pastoralist.

8. Household size and composition:

a). Male: _____

b). Female: _____

Milking mainly done by _____

Processing mainly done by _____

Selling mainly done by _____

9. Dairy herd size, herd composition and milk yield

	Breed	Number of milking	Yield per day (liter)	Lactation length (months)
Crossbred cows				
Local cows				
Others				

10. Output and disposal of milk and milk products

	Output (kg/lt)	Disposal (duration, days)
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a). Milk

Total produced

Total consumed

Total sold

Total processed

- into butter
- into cheese
- into yoghurt
- other

b). Pasteurized milk

Total produced

Total consumed

Total sold

c). Butter

Total produced

Total consumed

Total sold

d). Cheese

Total produced

Total consumed

Total sold

e). Yoghurt

Total produced
Total consumed
Total sold

f). Cream

Total produced
Total consumed
Total sold

11. Sales of products and prices

a). Raw milk	Unit	Response
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Sales outlet		
Buyer type		
Qty per day/week		
Price/unit		
Mode of payment		
Distance traveled/day		
Time spent/day		
Transport cost per day		

b). Cheese

Sales outlet		
Buyer type		
Qty per day/week		
Price/unit		
Mode of payment		
Distance traveled/day		
Time spent/day		
Transport cost per day		

c). Yoghurt

Sales outlet		
Buyer type		
Qty per day/week		
Price/unit		
Mode of payment		

Distance traveled/day
Time spent/day
Transport cost per day

d). Butter

Sales outlet
Buyer type
Qty per day/week
Price/unit
Mode of payment
Distance traveled/day
Time spent/day
Transport cost per day

e). Pasteurized milk

f). Cream

12. Tools and equipment for processing, preservation, transportation and storage of dairy products.

Name of equipment _____

13. Main problem(s) in production and sale or disposal of dairy products.

Product	Product related	Buyer related	Price related
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a). Raw milk

b). Pasteurized milk

c). Cheese

d). Yoghurt

e). Butter

f). Cream

Any other problem of your enterprise/business _____

14. Member of any cooperative or association or dairy development project?

Yes/No

If yes, benefits and obligations such as obtain credit, inputs, guaranteed sales outlets.

15. What inputs do you use and their sources?

a). Animal feed, b). Forage seeds, c). Fertilizer, d). Others _____

C. TRADER

16. Type of trader: a). Wholesaler, b). Retailer, c). Catering shop,

d). Other (specify): _____

17. Purchase of dairy products:

Product	Source	Nature of contract	Reason for choice of source	Qty/day/wk/month	Price/unit	Mode of payment	Distance Traveled/day (km)	Time spent/d	Mode of transport & Transport cost/day	How is product differentiated	How is price determined
Raw milk											
Pasteurized milk											
Cheese											
Yoghurt											
Butter											
Cream											
Other											

17.1. What quality tests do you conduct on your dairy products?

a). At collection centers: _____

b). At the laboratory: _____

18. Processing and storage by traders

Product	Qty processed/day/wk	Processing labour/day/wk/month	Other material cost/processing/ Preservation/day/wk	Rent for storage space	Periods of storage before sale	Losses, spoilage in storage
Raw milk						
Pasteurized milk						
Cheese						
Yoghurt						
Butter						
Cream						
Other						

18.1. Types and sources of labour _____

- a). Hired labour (permanent)
- b). Rented labour (Contract)
- c). Unpaid family labour)

19. Sale of dairy products in season (month)

Product	Sales outlet	Buyer type & Contract-Ual agreement	Reason for choice of outlet	How price determined	Qty/day/wk/month	Price/unit	Nature of contract	Mode of payment	Distance traveled/day, km	Time spent/day	Mode of transport & Transport cost/day	How Product differentiated
Raw milk												
Pasteurized milk												
Cheese												
Yoghurt												
Butter												
Cream												
Other												

19.1. What is the average income you get from your enterprise (income/day/wk/month/yr)?

20. Tools and equipment for processing, preservation, transportation and storage of dairy products.

- a). Milk cans
- b). Cream separator
- c). Butter churner
- e). Pasteurizer
- f). Freezer

Contractual payment for processing: quality _____ Cost/unit _____

21. Main problems with the sale and purchase of dairy products

Product	Problem related to purchase	Problem related to sale
Raw milk		
Pasteurized milk		
Cheese		
Yoghurt		
Butter		
Cream		
Other		

Any other problem of your enterprise/business _____

22. Are traders organized or linked in any formal or informal organization?

Yes/No. If yes, for what purpose?

D. PROCESSING ENTERPRISE

23. Type of enterprise: a). Private b). Gov't. c). Coops. d). _____

24. What products do you currently produce? Amount/day/wk (Lt, kg)

- a) Raw milk
- b) Pasteurized milk
- c) Ayib
- d) Formajo (hard cheese)
- e) Butter
- f) Cream
- g) Others

25. Products produced, installed capacity and utilization

Product	Plant capacity/day/wk/month	Actual production/day or week
Raw milk		
Pasteurized milk		
Cheese		
Yoghurt		
Butter		
Cream		
Other		

26. Raw materials/inputs used, their sources and prices

Raw material	Source & Contractual agreement	Reason for choice of source	Qty/day or week	Price/unit	Mode of payment	Farthest distance, km
Raw milk						
Powdered milk						
Packaging materials						
Animal feed						
Forage seeds						
Fertilizers						
Other materials						

27. Sale of dairy products in season (month)

Product	Sales outlet	Buyer type & Contractual agreement	Reason for choice of outlet	How price determined	Qty/day/ wk/month	Price/ unit	Mode of payment	Distance traveled/ day, km	Time spent/ day	Mode of transport & Transport cost/day	How Product differentiated
Raw milk											
Pasteurized milk											
Cheese											
Yoghurt											
Butter											
Cream											
Other											

27.1. Do you conduct any quality test on your dairy products? Yes/No.
If yes, what type?

28. Equipment, machinery, building

Asset	% used for dairy	Present value
Land		
Building		

29. Manpower

Type	Number	Total monthly wages
Skilled		
Unskilled		
Managerial		

30. Problem with purchase of raw materials and sale of products

Raw material	Problems related to purchase	Problems related to sale

Any other problem of your enterprise/business _____

General Questions to All

1. Is there any government or industrial control on prices of products? Which products? In what form? how is control on price implemented?

2. Is quality/standard of various products defined and enforced? How?

3. Is there any licensing requirement for farmers and traders? If so for what purpose?
How much does it cost?

4. Sources of credit for market agents, interest rates? _____

5. Do you have contractual agreement with your input (animal feeds, forage seeds, fertilizer, etc.) suppliers and buyers of your products?